

Integration of Optical and Microwave Data for Forest Mapping in Mongolia

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Abstract: This study aims to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of different classification techniques for extracting forest and other land cover classes using integrated optical and synthetic aperture radar (SAR) datasets. The analysis was conducted using multitemporal Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and Sentinel-1 SAR data, together with derived additional features. Three classification algorithms such as artificial neural network (ANN), support vector machine (SVM), and maximum likelihood classifier (MLC) were applied and compared. Among the tested methods, SVM demonstrated the most stable performance, achieving a maximum accuracy of 94.98% with a 35-feature dataset. The ANN classifier achieved the highest overall accuracy (95.87%) using a 22-feature combination. However, ANN performance decreased when additional derived features were included, highlighting the importance of optimal feature selection. In contrast, the MLC classifier produced lower and less stable accuracies, reflecting the limitations of traditional statistical classifiers when applied to complex multisource datasets. With respect to the discrimination of forest classes, the ANN method achieved the highest accuracy, followed by SVM, while MLC showed comparatively lower performance. Overall, the research demonstrates that machine learning classifiers combined with multisource satellite data significantly improve the classification accuracy of forest and other land cover classes.

Keywords: optical; SAR; classification; feature; Sentinel-1/2.

1 Introduction

Forests constitute one of the most valuable natural resources on Earth, providing a wide range of ecological, environmental, and socio-economic benefits. They play a critical role in regulating the global climate system through carbon sequestration, stabilizing soils, maintaining hydrological cycles, conserving biodiversity, and supporting food security and rural livelihoods (Amarsaikhan and Ganchuluun 2015). In addition, forests contribute significantly to ecosystem services such as habitat provision, water regulation, and climate mitigation. Consequently, accurate forest monitoring and mapping are essential for sustainable forest management and development planning in both developed and developing countries (FAO 2020).

Remote sensing (RS) technologies have long been recognized as effective tools for forest monitoring over large spatial and temporal scales (Borghi et al. 2025).

Traditionally, forest mapping has relied heavily on multispectral data acquired from optical sensors (Hirschmugl et al. 2017) due to their strong capability for vegetation discrimination and land-cover analysis. In recent years, integrated approaches combining optical and microwave data have gained increasing attention in forest mapping. The synergistic use of optical and SAR datasets provides complementary information about land surface characteristics (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). Passive optical sensors mainly capture spectral variations from the upper forest canopy, while microwave systems, due to their penetration capability, can provide structural information related to forest biomass, and surface roughness (Torres et al. 2012. Veloso et al. 2017).

Along with the increasing availability of multisource satellite data, machine learning algorithms have become widely used in RS image analysis. These algorithms are capable of processing large and complex datasets with diverse spectral, spatial, and temporal characteristics (Belgiu and Drăguț 2016, Elmahdy et al. 2022). Despite the growing popularity of machine learning techniques, parametric classifiers, such as the MLC, remain widely used in RS applications. These traditional statistical methods are often applied as baseline models for evaluating the performance of more advanced algorithms and remain important reference approaches in many classification studies (Maxwell et al. 2018, Amarsaikhan et al. 2024).

Therefore, systematic comparisons between machine learning and traditional classification techniques are still necessary to better understand their advantages and limitations when applied to complex multisource datasets. The objective of this study is to evaluate and compare the effectiveness of some classification techniques in extracting forest and other class information from integrated optical and SAR datasets. For this purpose, the ANN, SVM, and MLC were used, and their performance was systematically assessed using quantitative accuracy metrics. The analysis was conducted using Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery and Sentinel-1 SAR data, supplemented with derived spectral indices and additional features. The methodology was applied to a selected forest area in Mongolia with the aim of improving forest mapping accuracy and contributing to more reliable forest monitoring and sustainable forest resource management in the region.

2 Materials and methods

The area in Batsumber soum of Tuv aimag, Mongolia, was selected as the test site for this study (upper-left coordinate: 48°27'37.78"N, 106°45'28.19"E, upper-right coordinate: 48°27'37.78"N, 107°03'11.23"E, lower-left coordinate: 48°12'54.35"N, 106°45'28.19"E, lower-right coordinate: 48°12'54.35"N, 107°03'11.23"E). The study area is located in the central part of Mongolia, approximately 70 km north of the capital city of Ulaanbaatar.

Geographically, the area lies within the forest-steppe ecological zone, which represents one of the most important forested regions of Mongolia. Within this area, forest types include coniferous forests, deciduous forests, and evergreen forests. In addition to forest classes, the landscape also includes willows, grasslands, agricultural fields, bare land surfaces, and water bodies, forming a complex mosaic of natural and human-modified land cover types.

In the present study, the RS datasets used consisted of geocoded Sentinel-2A multispectral images acquired on 17 July 2025 and 5 October 2025, as well as Sentinel-1B dual-polarization SAR image acquired on 6 August 2025. Sentinel-2A images have 13 spectral bands and different processing levels (Sentinel-2 User Handbook, 2015). In our study, data with processing level-2A were used. The SAR data were presented in IW GRD format and had a pixel resolution of 10 m. Two different speckle suppression techniques, namely the Frost and Gamma-MAP filters, with window sizes of 3×3 and 5×5 were compared for noise reduction. After visual inspection of each image, it was found that the 3×3 Frost filter produced the best result in terms of delineating surface features as well as preserving texture information.

Color images of Sentinel-2A (with examples of available land cover classes) and Sentinel-1B of the target area are shown in Figure 1a and Figure 1b.

Figure 1. Color images of the target area: (a) Sentinel-2A imagery (with examples of land cover classes: 1- coniferous forest, 2-deciduous forest, 3-evergreen forest, 4-willow, 5-grassland, 6-agricultural field, 7-bare land, and 8-water), and (b) Sentinel-1B imagery.

As the study area represents a complex environment, it is important to derive additional features that are indirectly related to the reflectance or backscatter characteristics of the original bands of the selected optical and microwave datasets. Numerous spectral indices have been developed

to highlight forest, vegetation, soil, and other land cover types in remote sensing imagery. In this study, six optical indices were used, including normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), enhanced vegetation index (EVI), adjusted transformed soil-adjusted vegetation index (ATSAVI), red-edge index (REI), moisture index (MI), and moisture stress index (MSI), together with one SAR-based index (VV/VH) (Amarsaikhan et al. 2023) for the classification process.

In the present study, the following feature combinations were determined for the identification of the available land cover classes:

- 35 features, including 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, 6 spectral indices derived from Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 6 spectral indices derived from Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, and the VV, VH, and VV/VH polarization components of Sentinel-1.
- 22 features, including 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, and the VV and VH polarization components of Sentinel-1.
- 20 features, including 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025 and 10 spectral bands (Bands 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025.
- 19 features, including 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8A, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025, 6 spectral indices derived from Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025, and the VV, VH, and (VV/VH) polarization components of Sentinel-1.
- 10 features, including 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8A, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 17 July 2025 and 5 spectral bands (Bands 3, 4, 8, 11, and 12) of Sentinel-2 data from 5 October 2025.

In the final classification, we used and compared such classification techniques as the ANN, SVM, and parametric MLC for the discrimination of forest and other land cover classes in the selected test area.

For the ANN model, a logistic activation function was adopted, and the required parameters were iteratively optimized through repeated experiments. These parameters included the training threshold contribution, training rate, training momentum, training RMS exit criterion, number of training iterations, and number of hidden layers (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). The training threshold contribution, which ranges from 0 to 1.0, controls the influence of the internal weight on the node activation level. Similarly, the training rate varies between 0 and 1.0 and determines the magnitude of weight adjustment during training, where higher values generally accelerate the learning process. The training momentum parameter, also defined within the range of 0 to 1.0, influences the step size of weight updates, with larger values resulting in greater adjustment steps. The training

RMS exit criterion specifies the RMS error threshold at which the training process terminates (ENVI 2009). Following extensive experimental evaluation, the optimal parameter settings were determined as follows: training threshold contribution = 0.86, training rate = 0.20, training momentum = 0.79, training RMS exit criterion = 0.05, number of training iterations = 125, and number of hidden layers = 2. These optimized parameters were subsequently used to apply the ANN classifier to the selected feature combinations.

The SVM classifier employed in this study was implemented using a radial basis function (RBF) kernel. The RBF-based SVM transforms the input data into a higher-dimensional feature space, enabling the construction of an optimal hyperplane for effective class separation (Mountrakis et al. 2011). In this approach, two key parameters must be specified: the gamma parameter associated with the kernel function and the penalty parameter (Yang 2011). The gamma parameter controls the influence range of individual training samples. Lower gamma values produce a broader similarity radius, causing more samples to be grouped together, whereas higher gamma values restrict the influence range, requiring samples to be located closer to one another to be assigned to the same class. The penalty parameter represents the misclassification cost and regulates the balance between minimizing classification errors and maintaining a rigid decision boundary (Amarsaikhan et al. 2024). In this study, both gamma and penalty parameters were systematically adjusted through iterative testing to identify the optimal values for the classification task. Based on the experimental results, the gamma and penalty parameters were set to 0.48 and 93, respectively. These optimized parameters were subsequently applied in the SVM classification of the selected feature combinations.

The parametric MLC was implemented based on statistical decision theory under the assumption that all classes possess equal prior probabilities (Lillesand et al. 2015). The method assumes that the spectral values of each class follow a normal distribution and evaluates the probability of each pixel belonging to a particular class using class-specific parameters, including the mean vector and covariance matrix. Each pixel is subsequently assigned to the class for which it exhibits the highest probability of membership (Richards and Jia 2006).

For the accuracy assessment, several evaluation metrics can be employed, including overall classification accuracy, Kappa coefficient, F1-score, user's accuracy, and producer's accuracy (Lu et al. 2010). Since this study involved a large number of classification result comparisons, overall classification accuracy was selected as the primary evaluation metric due to its widespread use and straightforward interpretation. It is derived from a confusion matrix in which reference pixels are compared

with the classified pixels. Based on this comparison, an accuracy report is generated that indicates the percentage of correctly classified pixels relative to the total number of pixels (Nyamjargal et al. 2019).

3 Results

In the study area, to select training signatures from the combined optical and SAR images, initially, several regions of interest (ROI) representing the available classes were defined through accurate analysis. The separability of the training signatures was first checked in feature space and then evaluated using the transformed-divergence (TD) separability measure (ENVI 2009). After the investigation, the samples that demonstrated the greatest separability were chosen to form the final signatures. The final signatures included 1099 pixels for coniferous forests, 342 pixels for deciduous forests, 297 pixels for evergreen forests, 257 pixels for willows, 516 pixels for grass, 431 pixels for agricultural fields, 528 pixels for bare land, and 115 pixels for water, respectively.

For the accuracy assessment, random sample pixels representing each class were selected following a stratified sampling approach. The number of pixels assigned to each class was determined proportionally according to the spatial extent of the respective class. For example, larger classes, such as coniferous forest and grassland, were represented by a larger number of evaluation pixels, whereas smaller classes, including water bodies and willow vegetation, were represented by fewer samples (number of samples ranged from 129 to 1158). This approach ensured that the validation dataset adequately reflected the distribution and relative abundance of the classes within the study area, improving the reliability and representativeness of the classification accuracy assessment.

Table 1 presents a comparison of the overall classification accuracies obtained using the ANN, SVM, and MLC under different feature combinations derived from multisource data. As seen from Table 1, the results indicate that classification accuracy varies depending on both the type of classifier and the number and composition of input features.

Among the evaluated algorithms, the SVM classifier demonstrated the most stable and consistent performance across the tested feature combinations. The highest classification accuracy for SVM was 94.98% and achieved using the complete 35-feature dataset (Figure 2a). When the number of features was reduced to 22, 20, 19, and 10, the SVM classifier still maintained relatively high accuracies ranging from 93.18% to 94.12%. This relatively small decrease in accuracy suggests that SVM has a strong capability to handle high-dimensional datasets and feature

Table 1. Comparison of overall classification accuracies of SVM, ANN, and MLC.

Classification methods	35 features	22 features	20 features	19 features	10 features
SVM	94.98%	94.12%	94.09%	93.92%	93.18%
ANN	90.09%	95.87%	90.17%	87.56%	92.79%
MLC	92.36%	90.38%	92.07%	91.45%	86.24%

reduction, making it a robust classifier for RS applications where the number of available features may vary.

In contrast, the ANN classifier exhibited greater variability in performance depending on the selected feature combination. The highest overall accuracy observed in the experiment was 95.87%, which was achieved by ANN using the 22-feature combination (Figure 2b). This feature set consists of spectral bands from two Sentinel-2 acquisition dates and SAR polarization components (VV and VH) from Sentinel-1. The result indicates that the integration of multi-temporal optical data with radar information can significantly enhance classification performance when processed using a machine learning model such as ANN. The radar polarization features likely provide additional information about surface structure and moisture conditions that cannot be captured by optical imagery alone.

However, when a larger number of features was introduced, specifically the 35-feature combination, which also includes spectral indices and polarization ratios—the ANN classification accuracy decreased to 90.09%. This decline suggests that the addition of numerous derived variables may introduce redundant or less informative features, which can negatively affect neural network training and increase the risk of overfitting. Similarly, ANN performance decreased to 87.56% when using 19 features, indicating that the algorithm is more sensitive to feature composition compared with SVM. These results emphasize the importance of careful feature selection and optimization when applying neural network-based classification methods to remote sensing data.

The MLC showed comparatively lower classification accuracies across most feature combinations. The highest accuracy achieved by MLC was 92.36%, obtained when the full 35-feature dataset was used (Figure 2c). In contrast, the lowest accuracy (86.24%) occurred with the reduced 10-feature set, which consists only of selected spectral bands from Sentinel-2 imagery acquired on the two dates.

Figure 2. Best classification results obtained using: (a) SVM, (b) ANN, and (c) MLC. Land cover classes: 1- coniferous forest, 2-deciduous forest, 3-evergreen forest, 4-willow, 5-grassland, 6-agricultural field, 7-bare land, and 8-water.

However, compared with the other classification results, MLC provided the best separation of the water class.

In terms of separating coniferous, deciduous, and evergreen forests, as well as the willow class, the ANN method achieved the highest accuracy, followed by the SVM classifier. The performance of the MLC was satisfactory, but not as high as that of the other techniques.

4 Discussion

The results highlight the critical role of feature selection and multisource data integration in improving land cover classification accuracy. In particular, combining Sentinel-2 optical imagery with Sentinel-1 SAR data enhanced performance. Feature sets that included radar information (e.g., the 22-feature and 35-feature combinations) generally produced higher accuracies than those relying solely on optical data. SAR data provide complementary information related to surface roughness, forest structure, and moisture conditions, which are not always detectable using optical sensors alone (Torres et al. 2012). Consequently, integrating SAR polarization data with optical spectral bands improves the separability of land cover classes, particularly where optical spectral signatures are similar (Zhu et al. 2017).

Another important factor contributing to classification accuracy is the use of multitemporal satellite imagery. The inclusion of spectral bands from 17 July and 5 October 2025 allowed the classification models to capture seasonal variations in forest growth, moisture, and surface conditions. Multitemporal observations provide valuable information about phenological changes, increasing the spectral contrast between land cover classes and improving classification reliability. Previous studies have also shown that multitemporal datasets significantly enhance classification accuracy compared with single-date imagery (Pelletier et al. 2019).

However, increasing the number of features did not always lead to better results. While SVM and MLC performed well with the 35-feature dataset, ANN achieved optimal accuracy with 22 features, indicating that excessive features may introduce redundancy and reduce model generalization. Among the classifiers, ANN achieved the highest accuracy but was sensitive to feature configuration, whereas SVM showed the most stable performance across all feature sets. The MLC produced the lowest accuracies, reflecting the limitations of traditional statistical approaches for complex multisource data. For forest class discrimination, ANN performed best, followed by SVM and MLC techniques.

From the perspective of sustainable forest management and development planning, the high-accuracy land cover classification achieved in this study provides a reliable spatial information base for monitoring forest distribution, detecting land cover changes, and supporting evidence-based decision making. Accurate mapping of forest types and surrounding land cover enables resource managers to identify areas affected by degradation, track forest regeneration, and evaluate the impacts of land use activities.

The integration of multisource and multitemporal satellite data also facilitates continuous and cost-effective monitoring over large and remote regions, which is particularly important for countries with extensive forest and steppe landscapes. Therefore, the methodology developed in this study can support sustainable forest management by improving forest inventory assessments, guiding conservation planning, and assisting policymakers

in designing balanced land use and regional development strategies.

5 Conclusions

This study evaluated the performance of three classifiers for classification of forest and other land cover classes using multitemporal Sentinel-2 optical data and Sentinel-1 SAR imagery. The results showed that classification accuracy depended on both the type of classifier and the composition of input features. Among the tested methods, SVM demonstrated the most stable performance with the 35-feature dataset and maintaining high accuracies even when the number of features was reduced. The ANN classifier achieved the highest overall accuracy using the 22-feature combination, which integrates multi-temporal Sentinel-2 bands with Sentinel-1 polarization features. However, its performance decreased when additional features were included, highlighting the importance of optimal feature selection. In contrast, MLC showed lower and less stable accuracies, indicating limitations when applied to complex multisensor datasets. In distinguishing coniferous, deciduous, and evergreen forests, as well as the willow class, the ANN approach achieved the best accuracy, followed by SVM. While the MLC showed acceptable performance, it was less accurate than the other methods. Overall, the findings demonstrate that machine learning classifiers combined with multisource satellite data substantially improve land cover classification accuracy, emphasizing the value of Sentinel-1/2 data integration and appropriate feature selection for reliable RS applications.

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6 References

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